

Tool: Community contribution Canvas

Description	While an ongoing communication plan contributes to this stage as a “continuous recruitment” instrument, a specific goal of this tool is to negotiate and establish the levels of contribution to WeCount across participating citizens. These generally vary with respect to: (1) level of participation; (2) time available to dedicate to the pilot; (3) resources that can be brought into the pilot; and (4) relevant skills. The tool offers three different levels of contribution to the pilot across these four dimensions. It is very simple to use and understand.
Why am I doing it?	Collectively understand and establish the level of commitment of each participant to the WeCount pilot.
Which kind of issue can I tackle?	Potentially applicable to all citizen science projects
Resources needed	A3/A1/A0 printed Canvas (depending on the number of participants), post-its, pins, pens, one facilitator
Time needed	Between 40 minutes and 1 hour, depending on the number of participants
Skills needed (Not Required, Basic, Intermediate, Advanced)	<p>Subject-matter expertise: Basic</p> <p>IT skills: Not Required</p> <p>Facilitation skills: Intermediate</p> <p>Event organisation skills: Intermediate</p> <p>Project management skills: Intermediate</p> <p>Communication skills: Intermediate</p>
How to use the tool	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Organize a public workshop with the aim of establishing the extended research team, i.e. including citizens and all other relevant actors. As a result of this activity, those that participated so far and new members will officially become part of the pilot. 2. One facilitator explains the different variables describing the level of contribution to the pilot that each participating citizen can commit to. 3. Citizens position themselves onto the canvas by estimating and self-assessing the skills, resources, frequency of participation and time that each can bring into the pilot.
Outcomes	Initial pilot governance framework co-created and agreed across participants; commitment of citizens to the pilot.
Tips!	Be empath!